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Carbon offsetting in city climate action: role, determinants and characteristics

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ABSTRACT

To contribute to Paris Agreement objectives, non-state actors globally are setting voluntary emission reduction goals. Cities represent an important group with emission reduction plans, but vary in how they intend to meet targets. Some cities incorporate carbon offsetting to manage residual emissions. A lack of research exists on the role of offsetting in city plans, and better understanding this approach can inform city climate policy. This study uses a mixed-method design to explore the frequency, characteristics and role of offsetting in city climate action. We quantify how many cities globally include offsetting in their plan, create a random forest model to explore what characteristics of cities and their targets are associated with offsetting, and conduct a text analysis of city documents to explore how cities that intend to use offsets conceptualize the use. We find 363 cities globally with a population over 500,000 have a numeric GHG reduction target; 86 of these include offsetting in their plan. Larger cities, those with a higher per capita GDP, and those with more ambitious climate targets are more likely to offset. Further, of 44 cities included in our text analysis that intend to use offsetting, 29 discuss prioritizing emissions reductions but recognize that offsets will be needed for residual emissions. Less than half the cities discuss environmental integrity of offsets, and many lack detail on how to ensure integrity. Specifying concrete plans regarding offsetting and communicating these decisions is important for effectiveness and integrity of city climate action plans, knowledge sharing between cities, and planning for future offsetting.

Key Policy insights

- Most cities with a climate action target have yet to decide or publicly communicate whether they will use offsets to reach their target.
- Among cities that do intend to use offsetting, many lack details on estimating residual emissions, defining an upper limit on offsets, specifying from where and how to acquire offsets, and how to ensure environmental integrity.
- If used appropriately, offsets may allow cities to achieve more ambitious targets than otherwise possible.
- Additional guidance from city climate networks can help cities plan for high-integrity use of offsetting.

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1. Introduction

To contribute to 2015 Paris Agreement objectives, state and non-state actors have set ambitious greenhouse gas (GHG) emission reduction goals, including many with net zero targets (Green et al., 2024; Hale et al., 2022; Hsu et al., 2017). Achieving these goals will not be possible without actors drastically reducing emissions at the source (Rogelj et al., 2021). However, residual emissions, i.e. emissions that are uneconomical or technologically infeasible to abate by the target year, will need to be offset for actors to reach net zero (Broekhoff et al., 2019; Buck et al., 2023; Cooper et al., 2022; Tanzer et al., 2022).

Carbon credits are sold on voluntary or compliance markets and purchased by actors to offset emissions they are unable or choose not to reduce (Buck et al., 2023; Lovell & Liverman, 2010). Carbon credits originate from a range of projects, including avoided emissions (e.g. wind energy, avoided deforestation) and carbon dioxide removal (e.g. reforestation, direct air carbon capture and storage). Concerns have been raised regarding the effectiveness of offsetting (Hyams & Fawcett, 2013; Kreibich & Hermwille, 2021; Schneider & La Hoz Theuer, 2019), including additionality, permanence and leakage effects (Chiquier et al., 2022; Nabuurs et al., 2023; Tanzer et al., 2022). The effectiveness and ethics of using carbon offsets can be impacted by factors such as carbon accounting, impact on the credit user's own ambition, and price per credit (Kreibich & Hermwille, 2021; Michaelowa et al., 2019). The large variation in actors' approaches to emissions compensation as well as a lack of transparency around these strategies can obscure what is being done and with what effects (Frank et al., 2022; Lutzkendorf & Balouktsi, 2019).

Cities represent an important opportunity for climate change mitigation because over 50% of the world's population live in urban areas (Lwasa et al., 2023), and 80% of emissions are associated directly or indirectly with cities (Hoorweg et al., 2011; Seto et al., 2014). Further, the urban areas with the top 100 footprints (scope 3 emissions) are responsible for 18% of global GHG emissions, suggesting the potential of a limited number of local governments to significantly impact mitigation efforts (Moran et al., 2018).

Cities are increasingly developing emission reduction targets and climate action plans (CAPs) to meet these targets, although there is significant variation in the effectiveness of city climate action (Aboagye & Sharifi, 2024; Hsu et al., 2017; Wei et al., 2021). Past research on city climate action has focused primarily on GHG accounting (Balouktsi, 2020; Huovila et al., 2022; Lutzkendorf & Balouktsi, 2019), climate mitigation commitments (Hsu et al., 2017; Hsu, Brandt, et al., 2020; Hsu, Tan, et al., 2020; Kuramochi et al., 2020), or emissions reduction action (Damsø et al., 2017; Seto et al., 2021). However, there is no systematic research on the use of offsetting by cities, despite the fact that many cities rely on offsetting to reach net zero through the balancing of residual emissions or emissions outside the control of the city administration (Balouktsi, 2020; Huovila et al., 2022; Lutzkendorf & Balouktsi, 2019).

There is also a lack of research on the factors associated with a city's decision to use offsets, including whether offsetting is associated with ambition and/or integrity of city climate action. Limited research on net zero claims and the use of offsetting by companies has found the environmental integrity of corporate claims varies depending on the specific policies and the extent to which they rely on offsetting (Trouwloon et al., 2023). McLaren et al. (2019) recommend that entities set separate targets for emissions reductions and negative emissions, to avoid lowered ambition and overreliance on offsetting. Better understanding the determinants of offsetting by cities provides insight into the integrity of city CAPs and helps policy makers develop additional guidance to ensure offsets are used effectively.

Further, there is limited research on how cities that do intend to offset plan to implement their use. Balouktsi (2020) notes that emissions compensation by cities may occur either onsite, such as producing excess renewable energy, or offsite, for example the purchase of international carbon credits. Although different case studies on such activities exist (Damsø et al., 2017; Kebe et al., 2011), there is no consistent assessment as of yet. Lutzkendorf and Balouktsi (2019) state that guidance is lacking concerning the types of offsets cities should be permitted to use. Better understanding the use of carbon offsetting can provide insight into the effectiveness of this strategy in helping cities reach their net zero targets and in mitigating climate change.

In this study, we provide novel insights on the role, determinants and characteristics of carbon offset use by cities across the globe. To achieve this aim, we apply a random forest model (RFM) and a text analysis, and then integrate their results. This allows us to (i) quantify how many cities globally include offsetting in their

target, (ii) examine whether use of offsets is associated with city characteristics and/or ambition of mitigation targets, and (iii) explore what type of offsets are used, what role they play in city climate action, and what guidelines have been developed to help ensure high-integrity use of offsetting. Based on these analyses, we provide insights on the role that offsetting plays in global city climate action and recommendations for future use.

The paper is structured in the following way. After introducing the relevant literature on city climate action and carbon offsetting in Section 1, we then describe in Section 2 the methods used for data collection, creation of the RFM, and text analysis. Next, in Section 3 we present results from data collection (Section 3.1), the RFM (Section 3.2) and the text analysis (Section 3.3), then integrate these results and discuss key findings as well as opportunities for future research throughout Section 3. We discuss limitations of the current study in Section 3.4. Finally, in Section 4, we provide policy recommendations and conclusions of our study.

2. Methods

In this paper we use the term ‘offsetting’ to refer to the purchase of credits from outside a city’s boundaries. We use the term ‘insetting’ to refer to carbon dioxide removal (CDR) projects that occur within a city’s geographic boundaries. We use ‘emissions compensation’ as an umbrella term to refer to both offsetting and insetting.

2.1. Data collection

We use publicly available data on the use of offsets by cities from NetZero Tracker (NZT), Carbon Disclosure Project (CDP), and city climate action plans (CAPs). NZT (zerotracker.net) is a collaboration between the Energy & Climate Intelligence Unit, Data-Driven EnviroLab, NewClimate Institute, and Oxford Net Zero (Lang et al., 2024). NZT collects information on net-zero or similar pledges from cities, regions, companies and countries, including information on planned use of offsets (Lang et al., 2024). For cities, they analyse the CAPs of every city globally with a population over 500,000, a total of 1186 cities (Lang et al., 2024). Data is collected by a team of volunteers. The first author of the present paper volunteered with data collection to gain a better understanding of the process and contribute to the initiative. We use the cities dataset from NZT downloaded on 26 February 2024 (Lang et al., 2024).

CDP is a global disclosure system for companies, cities and regions to self-report their environmental impacts and initiatives. We use the 2023 Cities Emissions Reduction Targets dataset, downloaded on 20 February 2024 (CDP and ICLEI, 2024). Reporting to CDP is optional, thus not all cities covered by NZT are also included in CDP. However, for cities that have chosen to disclose to CDP, we use the data they provided to supplement and improve the accuracy of the data in NZT. Since we consider every city in the world over 500,000 people, we included all cities from NZT but only those from CDP that were also in NZT. Of the 1186 cities in NZT, 283 had reported to CDP. We used the dataset from the NZT, enhanced with data from the CDP, to create the RFM.

We also collected publicly available CAPs for a select subset of cities to enhance the data and as input for the text analysis (see Section 2.4).

2.2. Quantifying offset use by cities

From the initial set of 1186, a city was retained for analysis if it had a per cent emissions reduction target and target year reported in either NZT or CDP. This created a final set of 363 cities (Supplementary Material (SM) 2), 228 of which reported to CDP. We encountered occasional discrepancies in NZT data, such as a difference in climate targets reported in the NZT, city documents or the CDP data. When this occurred, we recoded with priority given to city CAPs, then CDP and then NZT (see also SM1.1.2).

We include four categories of responses to the (intended) use of offsetting by cities: *Yes*, *No*, *Maybe*, and *Not Specified*. A city was classified as *Yes* or *No* if they have reported a decision, *Maybe* if they have indicated they are considering offsets, and *Not Specified* if they do not discuss offsetting.

2.3. Modelling determinants of carbon credit use

We use a random forest model (RFM) to explore whether offsetting is associated with certain city characteristics or with characteristics of city CAPs. An RFM is a machine learning algorithm that generates many decision trees to predict the likelihood of classes based on characteristics of multiple predictor variables. A machine learning model was used instead of a traditional regression model because it has greater flexibility to capture complex and non-linear relationships within high-dimensional datasets (Pichler & Hartig, 2023). Moreover, RFMs make it straightforward to combine categorical and continuous predictors for classification tasks and generally outperform traditional multinomial logistic regression approaches (Wang et al., 2023). We use the ‘randomForestSRC’ package in the R software to produce 1000 decision trees. Model performance was assessed using a standard cross-validation approach. We used a 70%–30% split to randomly divide the data into training and testing data respectively. This cross-validation was repeated for 25 iterations, where in each iteration the data was randomly split, and the model was fitted on the selected training data and validated using the testing data.

We ran the RFM using the four classes of cities’ use of offsets as dependent variable (*Yes, No, Maybe, Not Specified*) and 11 predictor variables relating to city characteristics and the ambition and integrity of their climate target (Table 1). We selected the variables based on a literature review. Based on this review we also provide predictions for each variable in Table 1, discussed in more detail below the table and in SM1.1.3. Before fitting the models, we checked for multicollinearity in the determinants using the SpatialRF package in R to determine variance inflation factors (VIFs). We removed determinants with a VIF > 3 (Zuur et al., 2010) to obtain a non-redundant predictor set. As a result, we removed per capita GHG emissions. While there are inherently correlations between certain independent variables, for example C40 membership and population size, we determined these correlations to be below an acceptable level (Zuur et al., 2010) by checking for multicollinearity and ensuring all VIFs < 3.

In general, we predict high ambition and integrity, for example having an interim target, will increase the probability of both deciding to use or not to use offsets, while cities with lower ambition or integrity will be more likely to not decide about offsetting. Offsets may be used by cities with high ambition/integrity to compensate for residual emissions as a way of going beyond what is possible from reductions alone. Conversely,

Table 1. Dependent and independent variables, data sources and expected result (see SM1.1.3 for details).

Variable	Expected results
Offsetting ^{1, 2, 3}	Dependent variable: yes, no, maybe, not specified
Population ²	Larger cities more likely to use offsetting to reach neutrality.
Population density ⁴	Higher density more likely to offset due to limited space within city for sequestering residual emissions.
Per capita GDP ⁵	Higher per capita GDP positively associated with use of offsetting, as higher GDP provides greater ability to purchase offsets.
Final end target ^{1, 2}	Higher target is associated with use of offsetting as offsetting provides flexibility to set and achieve a net zero (100%) target.
Target year ^{1, 2}	An earlier end target year will be associated with use of offsets as it will be difficult to eliminate all emissions in a shorter time frame.
Interim target (yes/no) ^{1, 2}	Interim targets are a part of high integrity climate action, and therefore we predict having an interim target to be positively associated with making a decision (Yes or No) regarding offsetting.
Consumption emissions (yes/no) ²	Cities which include consumption emissions in their inventory are more likely to use offsetting, as city administration has limited control over these emissions and may rely on offsetting to balance.
C40 city (yes/no) ⁷	C40 membership is part of high integrity climate action, and therefore we predict having an interim target to be positively associated with making a decision (Yes or No) regarding offsetting.
Plan discusses equity (yes/no) ²	CAPs which include a discussion on equity will be less likely to use offsetting, as past research has explored equity and justice concerns relating to carbon offsets. ¹⁰
Reporting frequency ^{2, 8}	Regular reporting of emissions is part of high integrity climate action, and we therefore predict frequent reporting to be positively associated with having made a decision (Yes or No) about offsets.
Predicted emission change ⁹	We predict this variable to either increase or decrease the likelihood of offset use, depending on the specific political context.

¹CDP; ²NZT; ³City CAP; ⁴Calculated from city area and population from national statistics (people/ km²); ⁵2023 per capita GDP at national level at purchasing power parity (PPP) (IMF, 2023); ⁶Per capita country-level emissions for 2022, reported in tonnes of CO₂ equivalents per capita (Crippa et al., 2023); ⁷C40 website; ⁸Annual, Less than annual, No reporting mechanism; ⁹We took % change between a country’s 2015 emissions (year of Paris Agreement) and their predicted emissions in 2030 (de Elzen et al., 2022). ¹⁰(Nabuurs et al., 2023; Spash & Theine, 2016).

cities with high ambition/integrity may choose not to use offsets due to concerns about integrity, preferring instead to further reduce their own emissions. Limited research exists on the integrity of carbon offset use by cities, but research on companies has found integrity and ambition of offset use to vary depending on the specific policies and claims of the company (Trouwloon et al., 2023). Similarly, we predict the integrity of offset use by cities to vary depending on a city's policies and reasons for using/not using offsets. SM1.1.3 provides more detailed expected results.

We provide the above predictions to explain our rationale for including each variable in the RFM and to provide expected impacts based on past research. However, we do not individually test whether each prediction is supported or refuted by our model due to mixed accuracy of the RFM. The RFM provides Variable Importance Factors (VIMP) which show how much the inclusion of a variable in the model changes the accuracy of the overall model. The RFM also shows how each variable impacts the probability of being in each class of response to offsets. We discuss general findings from the RFM alongside results of the text analysis, but caution against over-interpreting results of individual variables from the RFM, especially those with lower VIMP (Figure SM.1).

2.4. Exploring the type and role of carbon credits in city climate action plans

To explore in more detail the trends that emerge from the RFM, we zoomed in on cities that have decided to use offsetting and conducted a text analysis of CAPs. Text analysis, also called thematic analysis or qualitative content analysis, is a common method for analysing qualitative data (Kuckartz, 2019). We limited the text analysis to the 54 cities that were identified by the NZT as using offsets because if a city reported to the CDP as using offsets but was not identified as such by the NZT, this is likely because it does not discuss offsetting in a publicly available document.

We systematically analysed the CAPs for each of the 54 cities, using a keyword search to identify relevant sections of the document. Keywords/ fragments include: offset, compensat*, credit, capture, storage, sequest*, CDR, sink (adapted from Sachdeva et al., 2022). We recorded information about the type, role and integrity of emission compensation strategies in city CAPs (SM1.1.4). When CAPs were available in both English and another language, the English version was used for analysis. When only available in another language, Google translate was used (SM1.4.2). When we found inconsistencies between the NZT and our analysis of city CAPs, we recoded our data to reflect our analysis, ultimately resulting in text analysis of 44 cities.

We present select quotations from city CAPs in the main text to illustrate key themes identified in the text analysis, and more information in Table SM.2. The complete text analysis coding table is available in SM2.

We discuss the results of the RFM and the text analysis together to identify key themes, policy recommendations and opportunities for future research, as neither the RFM nor the text analysis can independently provide a complete picture of how global cities use offsets.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Use of offsetting

Of the 363 cities included in our dataset, 24% use or intend to use offsets, while 22% of cities specifically indicate they do not (plan to) use offsets, 15% indicate maybe, and 39% do not specify their use or intention (Table 2). All eight geographic regions (Table 2) were represented in our dataset (Figure 1). Overall, we found most cities that intend to use offsets are not currently offsetting and intend to wait until at or close to their target year. This may help cities prioritize emissions reductions over offsetting, as noted by many cities, but can also make it difficult to plan for how many offsets will be required.

3.2. Determinants of carbon credit use

Our RFM results show how 11 predictor variables influence the use of offsetting (Figure 2). Variables with higher importance often have clearer patterns and therefore form the focus of our analysis. Larger (Figure 2(f)) and

Table 2. Characteristics of cities included in analysis.

Variable	Count or mean (% or 95% range) (<i>n</i> = 363)
Offsetting	Yes: 86 (23.7%); No: 81 (22.3%); Maybe: 53 (14.6%); Not Specified: 143 (39.4%)
Geographic region	Africa: 26 (7.2%); East Asia: 83 (22.9%); Europe: 88 (24.2%); Latin America and the Caribbean: 31 (8.5%); North America: 86 (23.7%); Oceania: 6 (1.7%); South Asia: 26 (7.2%); Western and Central Asia: 17 (4.7%)
Population	2,711,055 (200,545 ^a –14,914,800)
Population density (per km ²)	4,252 (367–15,817)
Per capita GDP (national)	46,599 (4,342–80,412)
Per capita GHG emissions (tonnes CO ₂)	8.9 (0.4–19.6)
Final end target	84.8 (18–100)
Final end target year	2044 (2023–2050)
Interim target	Yes: 215 (59.2%)
Consumption emissions	Yes: 42 (11.6%)
C40 city	Yes: 89 (24.5%)
Plan discusses equity	Yes: 106 (29.2%)
Reporting frequency	Annual reporting: 70 (19.3%); Less than annual reporting: 87 (24.0%); No reporting mechanism: 206 (56.7%)
Predicted national per cent change emissions 2015–2030	88.0 (47.0–179.8)

^aNZT used an external dataset to identify cities over 500,000 but used the cities' self-reported data to the CDP for their population column. This resulted in discrepancies due to differing definitions of city boundaries, including some cities reported to have a population below 500,000. This is a common issue, discussed further by Hsu, Yeo et al. (2020), which NZT hopes to address in future updates.

wealthier cities (Figure 2(e)) are for instance more likely to include offsetting in their plan compared to smaller and lower GDP cities, as are cities that have an interim climate target (Figure 2(d)), have a more ambitious end target (Figure 2(c)), are C40 members (Figure 2(b)), include consumption emissions in their target (Figure 2(k)) or discuss equity in their CAP (Figure 2(j)). Below, we discuss these variables in more detail.

Figure 1. Map of 363 cities included in analysis and their decision around carbon offsetting.

Figure 2. RFM results showing impact of 11 variables on the probability of four classes of responses to carbon credit use (Yes, No, Maybe, Not Specified) for 363 cities. For all parameter values/ categories, the probability adds up to 1. The sample size for each category is shown at the top of each panel for categorical variables. Variables are presented in order of overall importance in the RFM (see SM1.2.0).

3.2.1. Larger and wealthier cities more likely to offset

The RFM shows that cities with a per capita GDP greater than approximately \$40k/capita and cities with a population greater than approximately 6.3 million are more likely to say *Yes* to offsetting than *No*. There are multiple possible interpretations of why larger and wealthier cities are more likely to use offsets, and reasons may vary across cities due to differing rationale for using offsets. We integrate insights from the text analysis to further explore possible reasons.

First, the association between GDP and offsetting may be interpreted as wealthy cities buying offsets in place of meaningful climate action. Previous work has explored the ethics around wealthy actors purchasing offsets, whether to meet targets, alleviate guilt associated with emissions, or better sell products/ services (Hyams & Fawcett, 2013; McAfee, 2022; Spash & Theine, 2016). From the text analysis, this may be true for some cities, such as Houston, USA:

To account for and offset the emissions from existing fossil-fuel power generation, however, the global energy industry – much of which is based in Houston – must continue to develop new, cost-effective emissions-reduction technologies and strategies. Carbon capture, utilization, and storage (CCUS) and other negative emissions technologies are a key area of focus(...) (City of Houston, 2020).

Instead of divesting from fossil fuels, this suggests Houston is looking for offsetting strategies to meet targets while maintaining its fossil fuel industry. However, while this may be the case for a few cities, we did not find this interpretation to be reflected by most cities analysed. For example, Newcastle, GBR recognizes the potential downsides of offsetting:

Offsetting is often criticised because if a city (or company or country) can afford to offset, then under the system it doesn't need to make deep and meaningful cuts to its emissions.(...) Therefore, offsetting is the option of last resort in the hierarchy of mitigation of the city emissions(...) (Newcastle City Council, 2020)

Second, larger and wealthier cities likely have more funding to develop detailed CAPs and conduct emissions modelling, thereby recognizing it is difficult to reach absolute zero. In their paper on residual emissions in cities, Ulpiani et al. (2024) note that only front-runner cities in climate action have net-zero plans that reflect on the operational value of residual emissions. For example, London, GBR conducted extensive modelling through which they found it not technologically feasible to reach zero emissions by 2030:

While the Mayor's immediate priority is reducing emissions to reach net zero by 2030, Element Energy's analysis shows, even the most ambitious pathway would not achieve absolute zero carbon emissions by then. (...) Some offsetting will be needed to get to net zero emissions. (Greater London Authority, 2022)

Third, larger and wealthier cities are typically high emitters of GHGs and want to do as much as possible to decrease their net emissions. This is demonstrated in the CAP from Vancouver, CAN:

To capture our share of carbon recommended by the United Nations to limit warming to 1.5°C, we will need to capture carbon through land and aquatic-based projects outside Vancouver, too. (City of Vancouver, 2020)

Some large and wealthy cities may recognize their responsibility to quickly reach their fair share of carbon, a component of equity (Holz et al., 2018). Cities that discuss equity in their plan are more likely to say *Yes* to offsets than *No*. The positive correlation between cities that discuss equity in their CAP and saying *Yes* to offsetting further suggests some cities may use offsets as an additional measure to capture their fair share of carbon, beyond what is possible through reductions.

In contrast, smaller cities and those with a lower per capita GDP may face more barriers in acquiring offsets than larger and wealthier cities. These cities may have fewer resources available to develop detailed CAPs and calculate remaining emissions to offset or to purchase offsets, thereby having to rely on direct emission reductions. Alternatively, these cities may feel less obligation to offset residual emissions due to their relatively smaller historic contributions to global GHGs. While this study only included cities with a population over 500,000, future research could focus on the offsetting intentions of smaller cities.

3.2.2. Deciding on offsetting: C40 membership and interim target increase probability

While this paper focuses primarily on cities that include offsetting in their CAP, we also note interesting characteristics of the *No* class of cities, i.e. cities definitively ruling out offsets. Cities that have an interim target (Figure 2(d)) and those that are a C40 member (Figure 2(b)) are also more likely to have ruled out using offsets compared to those that do not have an interim target and are not a C40 member. Cities with a lower per cent reduction target (Figure 2(c)) are more likely to say *No* to offsets compared to those with a higher target, and cities that have annual reporting of emissions are most likely to say *No* to offsets while those with no reporting are least likely (Figure 2(a)).

Cities that have an interim target and/or are C40 members may be more likely to have a detailed CAP and therefore also be more likely to have decided about offsetting (*Yes* or *No*). These factors may also be associated with greater accountability or integrity, suggesting high integrity may be associated with both saying *Yes* and saying *No* to offsetting. The UN HLEG (2022) considers interim targets to be part of high integrity net zero targets and recommends that a net zero pledge include interim targets for each five years. Further, C40 cities are committed to having a 1.5C-aligned climate plan and to being on track to meet their plan as of 2024 (C40 Cities, 2023), both of which are aspects of ambition and integrity.

While the *Interim target* and *C40* variables increase the likelihood of saying *No* as well as saying *Yes* to offsets, cities that regularly report their emissions are more likely to say *No* to offsets and this variable had limited impact on the likelihood of saying *Yes*. In their report on global climate action, Yi Yeo et al. (2022) state that reporting of emissions is important for tracking progress and ensuring integrity. This suggests one aspect of high integrity climate action that is greater amongst *No* cities than *Yes*.

In this paper, we only performed a text analysis for cities that intend to use offsetting. Therefore, it is difficult to compare the motivations of cities that do intend to use offsets with those that do not. Future work could explore the cities that do not intend to use offsetting, including their rationale for avoiding offsets and their strategies for reaching zero emissions without offsetting.

Further, our study highlights the need for future research on the relationship between integrity and offsetting in city CAPs. As we have shown, aspects of high integrity are associated with both cities that do and those that do not intend to use offsets. Some cities may avoid offsets as they believe offsetting to lack integrity, while others may use offsets as an additional measure beyond what is possible through reductions alone. In addition to further exploring the reasons cities choose not to use offsets, future research could develop a framework to assess dimensions of integrity and how they relate to offset use by cities.

3.2.3. Many cities do not specify their offsetting plans

In contrast to the *No* and *Yes* cities, the RFM reveals several characteristics of the *Not Specified* class of cities that suggest a less developed CAP and potentially lower ambition. Cities without an interim target and those who are not members of the C40 are more likely to be *Not Specified*. In contrast to the *No* cities, cities with no reporting of emissions are most likely to be *Not Specified* while those with annual reporting are least likely (Figure 2(a)). Interestingly, cities with a higher per cent reduction target (Figure 2(c)) and a later end target year (Figure 2(h)) are more likely to be *Not Specified* compared to those with a lower target and earlier year. This may suggest that cities select a high (e.g. 100%) reduction target and a later target year (e.g. 2050) without yet having a clear plan on how they intend to meet this target. Cities with a low per capita GDP are also most likely to be *Not Specified* (Figure 2(e)), suggesting fewer resources available to develop a detailed CAP.

Those cities that have indicated they are undecided about their use of carbon offsets (*Maybe*) are the smallest class and the most poorly predicted class in the RFM. Cities with a lower population were more likely to be *Maybe* (Figure 2(f)) while those with a high GDP were less likely (Figure 2(e)). Cities that are not a C40 member (Figure 2(b)) and those with a reduction target around 60% (Figure 2(c)) were most likely to be *Maybe*.

3.3. Type and role of carbon credits in city CAPs

Studying 44 cities that intend to use offsetting, we identify nine themes relevant for better understanding the type and role of carbon credits in city CAPs (Figure 3). In the following sections we focus on the themes of

Reductions before offsetting, Predicted rather than current offsetting, Environmental Integrity and Regional offsetting as these themes have greatest policy relevance.

3.3.1. *Offsetting beyond emission reductions*

Results from both the RFM and the text analysis suggest many cities that intend to use offsets perceive offsetting as an extra step to achieve more ambitious targets than possible with reductions alone. From the RFM, the results of the *Final end target* and *Consumption emissions* variables support this. Having a higher end target increases the likelihood of saying *Yes* to offsets and decreases the likelihood of saying *No* (Figure 2(c)). Only 42 cities, less than 12% of the RFM sample, include consumption emissions in their target. Cities that include consumption emissions in their target are more likely to say *Yes* to offsets than *No*. Consumption (or scope 3) emissions are those that are generated outside of a city's boundaries as a result of consumption of goods and services within a city (Balouktsi, 2020) and failing to include them can result in a significant proportion of emissions being excluded from a city's inventory (Lutzkendorf & Balouktsi, 2019). While more cities are moving towards consumption-based accounting (Huovila et al., 2022), city administration often has limited control over consumption emissions, and therefore offsetting may be necessary.

In the text analysis, 29 cities (66%) note they intend to prioritize reductions over offsetting or discuss offsetting as a last resort for residual emissions. This suggests most cities that use offsetting intend to do so for emissions that are hard-to-abate or over which the administration has limited control, such as consumption emissions. Geneva illustrates this:

[Scope 3] emissions, as well as emissions linked to air travel by Geneva residents, may be subject to compensation if the reduction obtained is lower than the target objective. (translated from French) (République et canton de Genève, 2021)

If used appropriately, offsetting to achieve more ambitious targets may be considered part of high integrity climate action. UN HLEG (2022) recommends that carbon offsets be used for mitigation beyond an actor's value chain, which in the case of cities applies to consumption emissions. Therefore, offsetting can be an important part of city climate action going forward, allowing them to achieve more ambitious targets than would otherwise be possible. However, Ulpiani et al. (2024) note that residual emissions for cities change over time and continued efforts are needed to update their emissions reduction trajectories. It is important that city policy clearly limits the use of offsets to truly residual emissions and continually re-evaluates the emissions to be offset.

3.3.2. *Lack of clarity around ensuring environmental integrity*

The majority of cities (52%) note they will wait until at or close to their target year to offset remaining emissions. This is in line with recommendations from UN HLEG, which state that cities cannot count offsets toward interim targets in their emissions reduction pathway (UN HLEG et al., 2023). However, this can also delay the creation of concrete plans regarding offsets. Cities often lack clear decisions or guidelines around what type of offsets they intend to use and from where, making it difficult to evaluate the environmental integrity of planned offsetting. Less than half the cities (43%) mention environmental integrity of offsetting; those that do, often mention challenges but do not clarify how to address them. For example, Bristol, GBR states:

Achieving carbon neutrality (...) will typically involve offsetting; this is a complex issue, with challenges around additionality, fairness, financing interventions and carbon accounting. (Bristol One City, 2020)

While prioritizing reductions over offsetting is an important component of high ambition and integrity (Hale et al., 2022), cities should include in their plan detailed information on how they intend to ensure the environmental integrity of any future offsetting. Cities may face barriers to developing more concrete plans on offsetting due to a lack of resources to develop detailed CAPs or a lack of guidance on ensuring the environmental integrity of offsetting, or due to public scepticism around offsetting as noted by some cities. However, more explicitly stating plans for offsetting, including how to limit offsetting to residual emissions and how to ensure the integrity of future offsetting, will help cities contribute to meaningful climate action.

3.3.3. *Local versus distant offsetting*

Most cities in our text analysis intend to prioritize local or regional offsets over those from further away. All 44 cities are considering insetting in addition to offsetting, and 11 of the 44 cities intend to *prioritize* insetting over

offsetting. A further 15 cities note a preference for regional offsets (outside the city boundaries but closer than the national scale). This local/regional preference is generally due to co-benefits, and sometimes due to integrity concerns about offsets from further away. Brighton, GBR states:

Insetting is a mechanism to make more carbon removal projects happen locally; to enable better reporting of carbon reduction; to provide financial incentives and increase collaboration. (Brighton & Hove City Council, 2022)

Conversely, some cities discuss limited potential for carbon sequestration within the city due to space constraints. Washington, USA states: *'The District's land area is small, so our in-city potential is likely limited – perhaps ~1% of our total emissions'* (District of Columbia, n.d.).

The use of offsetting by cities may also be influenced by offsetting policies at higher administrative levels. Cities located in countries that reject the use of (international) offsets to meet targets will also be impacted by these national policies (and vice versa), as noted by Edinburgh, GBR: *'Scotland's target is a "net zero within boundary" target, meaning that the Scottish Government will not use international offsets to do its fair share to limit global warming'* (The City of Edinburgh Council, 2021). Future research could further explore the relationships between national/provincial and city policies around offsetting.

3.4. Limitations

We acknowledge some limitations of our analysis. First, regarding data collection, NZT data is collected by a team of volunteers. The NZT provides training to all volunteers and uses a draft and review system, where each data point is entered as a draft and then reviewed, although they do not collect data on intercoder agreement metrics. Interpretations of information may vary between volunteers, which could lead to errors in individual data entries, for example a city being incorrectly classified as using offsets when it actually discusses internal CDR (insetting) in its CAP. Furthermore, city reporting to the CDP is optional. This could result in a self-selection bias of which cities are included in this dataset, for example, if cities with more resources or a better-developed CAP are more likely to report to the CDP. The potential self-selection bias could result in offsetting actions of certain cities being missed from our analysis. This may contribute to the overrepresentation of larger and/or wealthier cities using offsets, however we attempted to mitigate this potential bias by combining CDP data with NZT data and our own review of city climate action plans. Additional discussion on limitations of the data used in the RFM is provided in SM1.4.1.

Second, regarding the RFM, cross-validation of our model shows it accurately classifies 50% of the data. The accuracy varies across the four classes, with the *Not Specified* class having the highest accuracy (80%), followed by the *Yes* (50%), *No* (38%) and *Maybe* (8%; for details see SM1.3.0). While results for the *Maybe* class carry limited meaning, we believe the overall accuracy of the model to be acceptable, especially when results are explored in combination with our text analysis. Better data availability may improve the accuracy of the RFM, for example if all cities with a climate action target consistently reported to the CDP. However, we also note that there are not always clear-cut relationships between predictor variables and a city's decision regarding offsets, and the use of offsets is often highly context-specific.

Third, in our review of CAPs, we relied on Google translate if an English version of the document was not available. Translations of key search terms may vary and the translated version of the document may not correspond with English search terms we used. This means we may not have captured all details on the use of carbon offsets by cities that do not have an English version of their CAP (see also SM1.4.2).

We do not believe the limitations noted above have had a detrimental impact on the results of this study. The aim of our study is to provide an overview of how cities around the world incorporate offsetting in their CAPs and to provide policy recommendations around offsetting by cities, not to provide an exact inventory of carbon offset use by cities.

4. Conclusions and policy implications

Our study provides novel insights on the frequency of offsetting by cities, identifies characteristics of cities that do (not) intend to use offsetting, and explores how cities that do intend to use offsets conceptualize their use.

We find that nearly a quarter (23.7%) of cities >500,000 people with a numeric climate target plan to use offsetting to reach their target. This highlights that offsetting will likely be an important part of city climate action in the following decades. However, our analysis also shows there is a general lack of clarity and detail around the use of offsetting in CAPs. In our dataset of 363 cities, the largest class of cities was the *Not Specified* class (39%), with a further 15% in the *Maybe* class. Moreover, many of the 44 cities that intend to use offsetting lack concrete decisions regarding offsets, including how many, what type, from where, and when. This lack of clarity suggests that most cities have not fully considered the potential role of offsetting in climate action. This may be due to a lack of resources or capacity, or not recognizing the importance of making and publicly communicating decisions around offsetting. However, communicating decisions and specifying concrete plans are important for accountability in terms of effectiveness and integrity of city CAPs, knowledge sharing between cities, and appropriate planning for future demand for offsets.

Given this lack of clarity on the use and integrity of compensation, there is a need for better guidance from city climate networks on how to define the use of offsets and what information to publish. Some guidance already exists about e.g. separate reporting of offsets and other inventory results (Fong et al., 2021), maximum levels of residual emissions (European Mission, 2021) or specifying such a limit (C40 & NYC, 2019). However, this and other guidance still lacks detail on the specific type of offsets allowed and methods to ensure the credibility of offsets (Balouktsi, 2020). Ulpiani et al. (2024) also note that there is no standardized method for defining residual emissions by cities. While Ulpiani et al. (2024) propose a conceptual framework to define the unavoidability of emissions, this framework has yet to be operationalized. Therefore, we highlight the need for better guidance from city climate networks, for example C40 or the Global Covenant of Mayors for Energy and Climate, that helps cities develop clear plans around the use of offsets. This guidance should include at a minimum: outlining how cities should define residual emissions following Ulpiani et al. (2024), setting an upper limit on the per cent emissions cities are permitted to offset, and providing guidelines to help cities ensure the integrity of offsets.

Further, we recommend that all cities intending to use offsets: define an upper limit on offsets; estimate how much and from what sectors they anticipate having residual emissions to offset; discuss from where and how they plan to acquire offsets; and detail how they intend to ensure the environmental integrity of offsets. While some cities provide some of this information in their CAP (e.g. Austin, USA; London, GBR; Helsinki, FIN), in this study we did not find any cities that provide all the necessary information to ensure high integrity use of offsets. If offsets are purchased from another jurisdiction or the private sector, cities should also consider in their plans how they will avoid the double counting of offsets, an important aspect of environmental integrity (Kreibich & Hermwille, 2021). Increasing explicit decision making and transparency along the lines of these recommendations can safeguard maximum emissions reductions and offsets being used with the greatest positive impact, and thereby allow cities to more significantly contribute to net zero goals.

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Author contribution statement

E.C., B.W., C.H. and S.H. conceptualized the overarching research goals and aims. E.C. collected data, analysed data for the text analysis, and drafted the paper. B.W., C.H. and S.H. provided input at all stages of the research and writing. S.H. made the random forest model and Figure 2 and assisted with writing text on the RFM. M.H. provided input on the overarching goals and aims, the RFM and the text.

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